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FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PERFORMANCE OF INTERNATIONAL NEW VENTURES: A STUDY OF SURGICAL INSTRUMENTS INDUSTRY OF SIALKOT, PAKISTAN

ABSTRACT

Growing attention has been paid to International New Ventures (INVs) which are small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) that internationalize shortly after establishment. There has been a considerable volume of research on International New Venture firms, but thus far there has been little research on factors influencing the performance of International New Ventures in the context of Asian economies such as Pakistan. To help to fill these gaps, this thesis examines the major economic and business characteristics of International New Ventures in the surgical instruments industry of Sialkot. The findings show that the government is not taking an interest to promote internationalization activities, but focuses on support only for export promotion. It is also found that International new ventures in the Sialkot surgical industry have a limited number of network relationships with customers and suppliers but have relatively few connections with government agencies. This research also investigates the performance factors that boost the performance of INV firms as the international business experience of managers and the use of networks and the subsequent effect on the capacity of INV firms to perform well in international markets.

The results provide evidence of the role of international business experience of managers and the business networks in foreign countries and the Government/Industry support to enhance the performance of INV firms in the international market. The implications of the findings for theory, recommendations, and future research are considered.

Keywords: International New Ventures (INVs), Surgical Instruments, Performance factors, born global firms, Sialkot Surgical industry

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INTRODUCTION

The Small and Medium size Enterprises (SMEs) sector is flourishing in developed countries with more than 90% contribution in the GDP. This sector has become the backbone of the economy of developed and developing countries. However, the role of SMEs in developing & developed nations has been increased (Wictor, 2012). In Pakistan, there is a great opportunity for SMEs sector to progress and contribute towards the GDP of the country. The real GDP growth of the country is 3.6% for the year 2013-13 which is low as compared to 4.4% of previous year 2011-2012. The SMEs sector has gone through dynamic changes over the past few years and the government of Pakistan is taking serious action to promote and strengthen the SMEs sector throughout the country. The serious steps towards the development of SMEs from government are evident with the recent national consultation conference held in Islamabad entitled “**Vision Pakistan 2025**”. The emphasis has been given to boost the economy through entrepreneurial activities from the grass root level in Pakistan. Moreover, it has been discuss in the conference that export and private sector-led growth can be achieved through entrepreneurship in the country.

The Government of Pakistan constantly engaged in the formulation and implementation of policies to help small businesses in the economic development of the country. During the last decade, the Government of Pakistan has established various institutions like SMEDA to overcome challenges of SMEs and to assist new business ideas. There is need to explore the deprived sectors of the SMEs which requires proper attention for technological development which result in better performance in international markets.

Today, the knowledge-based economy has increased the importance of entrepreneurship due to the innovation in technology and economic development. The central focus of the entrepreneurial process is to discover and develop the promising business opportunities around the world. The academic research scholars have admitted the prominent role of SMEs in international entrepreneurship and in global trade. They have also admired the promising role in the rapid transformation of knowledge and managerial skills in the international arena.

The speed of internationalization of SMEs has become possible due to the intensive global competition and rapid technological advancement. The world is witnessed that new forms of small firms have been emerged due to the intensive global competition and rapid technological advancement. The unique form of small firms like “International new ventures (INVs)” also termed as “Born Global” are the new form of SMEs due to their orientation towards export in foreign countries within the inception of more or less 3 years (Oviatt and McDougall, 1994). These forms are playing their vital role in strengthening the business economy of different countries. In Pakistan, these forms of firms are working in surgical instruments industry and sport industry of Sialkot. This concept is known as “Entrepreneurship”, and it is prevailing in Pakistan over the past 3 decades. Jennifer et al., (2009) explain that “... *entrepreneurship in general is the phenomena to capitalize on identified opportunities or creation of new opportunities through innovation*”. The traditional theories of SMEs internationalization suggest that firms should go global by following the step-by-step process after serving and learning from the domestic market (Johanson & Vahlne, 1977), but International new ventures (INVs) firstly acquires the international business experience and develop the foreign networks and then they start to internationalize (Kuivalainen, 2001). The phenomenon of International new ventures is increasing in emerging country like Pakistan. These SMEs are found in large numbers in surgical instruments industry of Sialkot, Pakistan. These firms are unexplored in developing countries, particularly in Pakistan. The performance of these firms are stagnant over the past few years due to the lack of resources, international business experience of Managers/CEOs, Business networks in foreign countries and government/industry support. The entrepreneurs need to utilize internal and external resources efficiently in order to achieve high performance in the international markets. The high performance of these firms will result in sustainable industry growth and significant contribution towards the GDP of the country.

The economic growth rate of Pakistan is 2.9% during the last five years which is very low as compared to neighboring countries like, Bangladesh and India. The real GDP growth of the country has been estimated at 3.6% for the year 202-13 which is 0.8% less from the previous fiscal year 2012 Pakistan Economic Survey 2012-13, the manufacturing sector has 13.2% share in GDP whereas growth of the manufacturing sector is estimated at 3.5% in current year which is very poor with respect to country like Pakistan. According to economic survey of Pakistan, the growth rate of small scale manufacturing firms is estimated at 8.2% for the year 2012-13. Again this rate is very low as compared to other developing countries in the Asian region.

According to the Pakistan Economic Survey 2012-13, there are five leading export sectors of the Pakistan economy, these are: Sport, Surgical, Carpet, Textile and Leather. In the years 2010-11, the total export from Sialkot was US\$260 million. This has increased significantly and reached the US\$300 million mark in the fiscal year of 2011-12 and US\$303 million in 2012-13 (SIMAP, 2013).

In manufacturing industry, this study focuses on surgical instruments industry of Sialkot, Pakistan. The surgical instruments industry of Sialkot is also called “Sialkot Surgical Cluster”. Sialkot surgical cluster is recognized as one of the successful surgical instrument industries by exporting one fifth of

the surgical instruments in the global market (Nadvi, 1999). Due to the increase in demand and globalization, the surgical instruments have become the major world's export goods in many countries. The INV firms in this industry are not performing well in the international market. The performance of these INV firms in international market does matter because of their orientation towards export is evident as more than 90% of their sales derived from export in foreign countries. There are certain factors which can enhance the performance of these INV firms in surgical instruments industry of Sialkot, these factors are discussed in this study to address the performance of INV firms in surgical industry.

Business networks are very important for INV firms to grow and increase export volumes in foreign countries. Oviatt and McDougall (1994), Bell (1995) and Coviello and Munro (1997) suggest that you have to study the networks of the company to understand the performance of small firms like International new ventures. The business networks are playing vital role in term of knowledge spill over (Transfer of knowledge). The business relationships provide support to INV firms in; Product development for foreign markets, Developing foreign market intelligence and R&D for foreign market development. This result in growth of INV firms in international market. In addition to the international business experience of managers/CEO and business networks in foreign countries, there should be government and industry support to the INV firms. Particularly in Pakistani SMEs context, government should provide financial support and advisory to the INV firms to grow.

The surgical industry of Pakistan is not playing its vital role as to where it require to insert its sincere effort in establishing the skill building institutes, building industry-university research linkages in order to strengthen in INV firms in surgical sector. Since INV firms are important sector of the economy, factors that influence the performance of INV firms must be established to contribute significantly in the economy of Pakistan. According to Surgical Instruments Manufacturers Association of Pakistan, in the years 2010-11, the total export from Sialkot was US\$260 million. This has increased significantly and reached the US\$300 million mark in the fiscal year of 2011-12 and US\$303 million in 2012-13 (SIMAP, 2013).

This study is intended to investigate the research gap of factors influence the performance of INV firms in surgical instruments industry of Sialkot, Pakistan. The establishment of these performance factors will result in tentative solution and strategies for the entrepreneurs in surgical industry to adopt in order to increase the performance of these firms in the international market and the level of employment and economic prosperity in the country.

Research Question

Based on the above discussion and research gap, this thesis develops one research question:

- What factors influence the performance of International new venture firms in the surgical instruments industry of Sialkot, Pakistan?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theory of International New Ventures (INVs)

The phenomenon of International new venture is being widely discussed among the researchers of international business, international entrepreneurship and international marketing. One of the successful papers of Oviatt and McDougall (1994) on international new venture, titled as "Toward a Theory of International New Ventures" has attracted the significant attention of researchers around the world. According to Oviatt and McDougall (1994), International new ventures (INVs) are "business organizations that from inception seeks to derive significant competitive advantage from the use of resources and the sale of outputs in multiple countries" (p. 46).

Various terms and definitions During the period of 1990s when INVs started their emergence in international market, many researchers have tried to describe the emergence and existence of this newly developed phenomenon (Luostarinen & Gabrielsson, 2006, McDougall, et al., 1994; Rialp, et al., 2005). Since then, various terms have been invented to explain the similar phenomenon. The most used term is *International New Venture (INV)*, which is invent by Oviatt & McDougall (1994), and they defined INVs as firms that "from inception, seek to derive significant competitive advantage from the use of the resources and the sale of outputs to multiple countries". They also classify INVs in four types which are given in figure 2.1 and various definitions of INVs in Table 2.1.

Table 1

Various Definitions of INVs

Author	Term	Definition
Bell et al (2001)	Born-again globals, extension of the born global phenomenon	"Typically, these are well-established firms that have previously focused on their domestic markets, but which suddenly embrace rapid and dedicated internationalization." This typically happens following a critical event: change of management, drastic change in firm strategy, management buyout, following an MNC customer, or acquisition by another firm.
Di Gregorio et al, (2008)	INV	INVs are seen as arising from the cross-border nexus of individuals and opportunities. Some INVs may result from opportunities to leverage domestically based resources across national borders; others are created to exploit opportunities for novel combinations of international resources. INVs may also simultaneously engage in cross-border combination of resources and international market expansion.
Gabrielsson, Kirpalani (2004)	Born global	"For the purpose of this article, it is enough to conclude that born globals from their inception pursue a vision of becoming global and often globalize rapidly without any preceding long term domestic or internationalization period."
Knight & Cavusgil, (1996)	Born global	"small, [usually] technology-oriented companies that operate in international markets from the earliest days of their establishment"
Knight (1997:1; in Moen, 2002)	Born global	"a company which, from or near its founding, seeks to derive a substantial portion of its revenue from the sale of its products in international markets."
Knight & Cavusgil, (2004)	Born global	"business organizations that, from or near their founding, seek superior international business performance from the application of knowledge-based resources to the sale of outputs in multiple countries."
Knight, Madsen & Servais (2004)	Operational definition of a born global	"firms less than 20 years old that internationalized on average within three years of founding and generate at least 25 percent of total sales from abroad."
Kuivalainen et al (2007)	Apparently born global vs. genuine born global	'Apparently born global' or 'born international' are the firms exporting only to close markets, with the export ratio of 25 percent (an arbitrary cut-off point). 'Genuine born globals' are the firms that operate in distant markets and multiple regions and fulfil more or less the definition of a global firm as per Levitt, 1983.
Luostarinen &	Born global vs.	"International firms are firms for which international business is the largest source of revenue (over 50% of total sales) and

This definition has been further adjusted to fit into the context of many companies in Sialkot surgical instruments industry. For these companies, it is important that sales to multiple countries are included in the definition so that investigation is meaningful in its own environment. This builds on the fact that the International new ventures (INVs) are operating in multiple countries. In other words, the entrepreneur starts with a vision that the company should widen its domain abroad because he sees a potential market there. Or it could be that he is forced to act likewise since the product is a niche product and the domestic market is too small or export opportunities are significant.

Surgical Instruments History - World Overview

According to the report of Transparency Market research, the global surgical instruments market was worth of 5.2 USD billions in year 2011 and expecting to have fasted revenue growth at 7.5% during 2011 -2017. Businesses dealing in surgical instruments have a globally recognized importance. Renowned markets in the world for this niche include, US, Europe and Japan. As for the history of this phenomenon, it goes all the way back to a place called Tuttlingen, which is located in Germany and is famed for its functional surgical tools (Nadvi & Halder, 2002). The past life of these surgical instruments is ancient indeed and has roots in the 17th century. Evidently that was when these surgical instruments were used for the first time.

Currently, the United States of America is at the top with regard to this particular type of business. It is the leading manufacturer because of its advanced state of technology. A record number of medical paraphernalia and surgical goods are churned out in the land of opportunity (Themedica, 2009). In the capacity of an industry, it happens to be very competitive and price-susceptible. This is because the demand for high technology remains at an all-time high. The closure devices cover 41% of the net world market share (Faisal, 2010). Most of the multinational corporations and manufacturers which are busy in this sector of the economy comprise small medium-sized enterprises. All of them are located in North America not to mention Western Europe (Germany) and Sialkot (Pakistan).

In the early stages of the 20th century, there were some clusters such as “Sheffield” which is located in the UK; “Nogent-Sur-Marne” in France as well as two in “Solingen & Tuttlingen” (Germany). All the others except for Tuttlingen have been destroyed. In recent years, Malaysia, Poland, Hungary, China, Korea and India have also extended their services for the surgical industry sector (Surgical Instruments Manufacturing Association of Pakistan - SIMAP 2013).

Surgical instruments industry of Sialkot Pakistan

The Sialkot surgical cluster started regional production in 1890, so it has deep indigenous roots. The inception of business began between the ironsmiths of Sialkot and British doctors who obtained valuable services from this industry by having certain instruments repaired. When the “Memorial Christian Hospital” was founded it gave a leading edge to this industry in Pakistan (which was then a part of the Indian Subcontinent). The British doctors were quite impressed by the manufacturing capabilities and the high-quality durable products. In the beginning, they ordered scalpels and were quite satisfied with the results. So, finally, the Sialkot surgical industry got an order of spatulas and different kinds of knives which were used in surgical operations.

With the passage of time, the Sialkot surgical industry achieved a lot of popularity and the hospitals located in British India started buying surgical and dental instruments from this location. By 1920, the industry was well-established and by 1930, Sialkot became a successful regional exporter. Gradually, Pakistan initiated the exports to overseas regions. Mainly the instruments went to England, Egypt and Afghanistan. During WWII, the British ordered the Sialkot industry to manufacture surgical instruments which were particularly used by the Allied Forces. The Metal Industries Development Center (MIDC) was laid down for the inspection of these instruments. Additionally, quality monitoring began its operations via this center.

The industry started its expansion of exports on a large scale. Upgrading of MIDC was accomplished twice, once in 1947 and later on during the 1980s. Production of better results by a combination of new technologies such as drop forging hammers and vacuum heat treatments helped immensely in the streamlining of instruments. By the 1990s, there were a few joint ventures with European and American firms. AMERI TRADE is an example. The conglomerate’s office was set up in the city of Sialkot to monitor quality control before the final export of surgical instruments to key markets in North America and Western Europe. At present, Pakistan has made an image for itself by exporting quality instruments, among which surgical and dental odds and ends of equipment form the largest chunk. In the years 2010-11, the total export from Sialkot was US\$260 million. This has increased significantly and reached the US\$300 million mark in the fiscal year of 2011-12 and US\$303 million in 2012-13 (SIMAP, 2013).

Growth of International New Ventures (INVs)

Although resources are assumed to play a critical part in the growth of Born Globals, they suffer from resource limitations (Oviatt & McDougall, 1994), quantity of resources (Hannan, 1998) and fungible resources (Sapienza, et al., 2006). Managerial experience in terms of stock, stream, and variety (Reuber & Fischer, 1999) are also considered important components of growth. However, resources as such do not make for much growth if firms do not possess the necessary capabilities for deploying and coordinating the various resources (Verona, 1999). Based on previous studies, long-term growth may only be achieved if these capabilities are of a substantive and dynamic nature (Zahra, et al., 2006). The Comparison of Growth of Traditional SMEs and INVs is shown in figure 2.2.

In addition, entrepreneurial orientation should be at a peak point (Knight & Cavusgil, 2005) and the founders and management team members should be highly experienced so that the firm does not suffer from lateral rigidity (Luostarinen, 1979). For the fact is that this may limit firms from exploring new opportunities and methods. Instead they would then go with the known alternatives. Finally, high industrial growth rates and levels of globalizing enablers are expected to provide growth opportunities (Oviatt & McDougall, 1994). These industries and firms are assumed to be critical drivers in reaching commercial breakthrough (phase 2) and global breakthrough (phase 3). These factors may also start global rationalization (phase 4) but in a reverse manner. In other words, when industry growth slows down, the need for firms to rationalize their activities globally is enhanced, driving the need for resource alignment (Douglas & Craig, 1989). Greater concentration of sellers (Driffield & Munday, 1997) also increases the need to rationalize.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1 Theoretical Framework

HYPOTHESES

H1: *There is a relationship between the international business experience of managers/CEOs and performance of INV firms in the surgical instruments industry of Sialkot, Pakistan*

H2: *There is a relationship between the business networks in foreign countries and performance of INV firms in the surgical instruments industry of Sialkot, Pakistan*

H3: *There is a relationship between the Government & Industry Support and performance of INV firms in the surgical instruments industry of Sialkot, Pakistan*

METHODOLOGY

There are two types of sampling techniques are used in research: probability and non-probability sampling. Research indicates that non-probability sampling can be used in quantitative studies (Merriam, 1988). Non-probability sampling is used in this study because the characteristic of the whole population of this study is unknown. Thus, purposive sampling is used for this study which is also known as judgmental sampling or criterion based sampling. It is used to explore the in depth understanding of the phenomenon (Marriam, 1988, p. 48). According to Malhotra and Birks (1999, p.364), the judgmental sampling "is a form of convenience sampling ... in which the researcher ... chooses the elements to be included in the sample because he or she believes that they are representative of the population of interest or are otherwise appropriate."

Correlation Analysis**Table 5***Correlation Analysis*

		Correlations			
		FP_Comp	GINDSP_Com	IBE_Comp	BNT_Comp
			p		
FP_Comp	Pearson Correlation	1	-.174**	.129*	.077
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003	.027	.188
	N	294	294	294	294
GINDSP_Comp	Pearson Correlation	-.174**	1	.626**	.562**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003		.000	.000
	N	294	294	294	294
IBE_Comp	Pearson Correlation	.129*	.626**	1	.935**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.027	.000		.000
	N	294	294	294	294
BNT_Comp	Pearson Correlation	.077	.562**	.935**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.188	.000	.000	
	N	294	294	294	294

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation

There is a significant relationship exist among three variables, which means that Government and industry support and international business experience has significant influence on firm's performance because sample response is significant in both cases. The results of 2 tailed level of significance, shows that the value is less than 0.05 which means that there is a significant relationship exists between the observed variables. However, In case of Business networks, it shows the insignificant level which is .188. There could be the one reason of not meeting the demand of foreign buyers after developing business networks with them. Although business networks in foreign countries are significant with other two variables i-e Government & Industry support and International business experience of managers/CEOs.

Regression Analysis

In regression analysis, liner regression is used to analyze the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. The purpose to use this analysis is to find out the relationship of the dependent variables with independent variable used in the model.

Table: 6*Model Summary***Model Summary^d**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.382 ^a	.146	.137	.72734

Interpretation

The value of R^2 (R Square) is 0.146, which means that 14.6% of the total variance in firms' performance has been explained. It can be considered as not impressive but still not bad either. There are many factors which influence the performance of INVs like Quality standards of the product for foreign markets, economies of scale production which result in low fixed cost and low variable cost comparatively as well. These factors do not come under the scope of this study due to limited resources and time.

Table: 7

Analysis of Variance

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26.268	3	8.756	16.551	.000 ^a
	Residual	153.419	290	.529		
	Total	179.687	293			

a. Predictors: (Constant), BNT_Comp, GINDSP_Comp, IBE_Comp
b. Dependent Variable: FP_Comp

Interpretation

The Table 5.10 indicates the statistical significance of the regression model that was applied. Here, $p < 0.0005$, which is less than 0.05, and indicates that, overall, the model applied can statistically significantly predict the outcome variables.

Table 8

Performance factors of International new ventures

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Tolerance
1	(Constant)	1.897	.145		13.044	.000		
	GINDSP_Comp	-.422	.068	-.435	-6.229	.000	.604	1.656
	IBE_Comp	.860	.174	.805	4.931	.000	.110	9.054
	BNT_Comp	-.429	.153	-.432	-2.804	.005	.124	8.045

a. Dependent Variable: FP_Comp

Interpretation

Table 5.11 describes that the relationship of variables are significant. However, B value of Government & Industry support shows -.422 and the B value of Business networks shows -.429. These two variables describe the inverse relationship with performance. In this case the government intervention has negative effect on firm's performance i-e export barriers, custom clearness hurdles and increase in taxes etc. In case of business networks, the firms are unable to cope with the demand of international markets on time. The quality of products matters a lot in the foreign markets that can destroy the business relations as consequences.

Comprehensive Discussion

The research model is designed to capture the relationships between key factors and the international performance of International new ventures and yields important insights into the international activities and performance of these firms. By conducting empirical tests for the associations, this study provides complementary support to previous qualitative studies of the international business experience of managers and the business networks. For Instance, since Oviatt and McDougall (1994), individuals with international business experience and international entrepreneurship have been as an essential requisite for the growth of International new ventures.

To sum up, although plenty of studies based on qualitative insights have been conducted, empirical evidence using large sample sizes remains limited. By taking a quantitative approach to investigating antecedents and their effects on the international performance of International new ventures, the present research is complementary to the literature based on the quantitative approach and responds to calls for empirical tests in the research of International new ventures to generalize findings (e.g., Freeman et al., 2006, Freeman and Cavusgil, 2007). This study also contributes to a theoretical extension of International new venture research, responding to Freeman et al (2006: 60) claims that "given the paucity of quantitative research on the International new ventures (INVs) phenomenon, considerable research must be done to develop valid measures of the dependent and independent variables and measures for testing the hypothesized relationships between them".

Discussion

This study investigated 294 INV firms to explore the factors influence their performance. It has been found that all three independent variables i-e Government & Industry support, international business experience of managers/CEOs and Business Networks are correlated with the performance of international new venture (INV) firms in surgical instruments industry of Sialkot, Pakistan. The International business experience of managers/CEOs is positively correlated with the firm performance whereas Government & Industry support and Business networks in foreign countries are showing inverse relationship. There are many reasons behind this, for instance, in case of Government & Industry support, there are many hurdle for the INV firms to tolerate the tax expenses, export duties etc. The Government intervention is causing the problem in the way of success of INV firms in surgical instruments industry of Sialkot. Moreover, business networks in foreign countries having inverse relationship with respect to the performance of INV firms. This inverse relationship describes the gap of international supply and demand; the INV firms in Sialkot are unable to meet the demand of foreign customers which in result reduce their performance. The quality of the product is also a solid reason behind the inverse relationship of business networks and firm's performance. The manufacturers in Sialkot surgical instruments industry are lacking with latest technology which is the big hurdle in the way of producing quality products particularly in medical instruments.

The findings suggest that the international business experience of managers has an important role to play not only in enhancing the capacity to boost international performance, but also in forming valuable business network links. The business networks leads to significant enhancement in foreign performance capacity, thereby improving international business performance. To sum up, these results provide empirical evidence of an association between

the key variables for performance of International new ventures of Sialkot surgical instruments: the international business experience of managers affects the use of networks and subsequently influences foreign performance capacity and this capacity boosts foreign market performance (Oviatt and McDougall, 1995). The results imply that strategic use of the IBE of managers and networks lies at the heart of the international growth potential and performance of International new ventures.

This research suggests that a network for foreign activities is a construct which is comprised of multiple dimensions: the value of the network and the number of networks. In an effort to measure network frequency, the extant literature has mostly used numerical scales by using questions such as “*How many contacts does your firm have?*”. It is unlikely however that such a measurement method adequately takes into account variation in network range which may be triggered by firm size. Thus, larger INV firms are more likely to have more network connections compared to smaller INV firms.

Conclusion

This study emphasizes the central role International business experience in leading to improvements in the international business performance of International new ventures. The findings confirm that business network is a significant driving force of international business performance in areas such as satisfaction with foreign market growth, share of sales from international activities, and the number of foreign markets supplied. In addition, it is found that government & Industry support has a direct effect on the performance of International new venture.

Although some of the literature assumes strong linkages between individuals with international work experience, international networks and business performance of International new ventures, the present study provides empirical evidence of the relation of international business experience, business networks and government & industry support in achieving superior international performance. Consistent with Knight and Kim (2008), the findings suggest that international business performance and the survival of the firm appear to be the turning point on the extent of the foreign performance capacity.

The findings indicate that the international business experience of managers is a key predecessor, influencing both foreign performance capacity and the value of networks. It is most likely that managers with international business experience in a variety of domains such as R&D, client and customer management and international sales have their own personal networks in particular business domains.

The managers & Entrepreneurs in International new ventures are therefore advised to seek to take full advantage of a strategic use of their international business experience so that the firms can make valuable contacts for international activities and enhance their capacity to achieve superior foreign performance (Bell et al., 2003).

Of particular importance to International New Venture firms is the use of networks for foreign activities as they have the potential to determine foreign performance capacity and thereby international performance outcomes.

The findings of this research suggest that the use of networks is more important to foreign performance capacity than the international business experience of managers in small firms. This supports the view that effective network building is important. In relation to the networks, this research highlights that the relationship has multiple dimensions: the value of networks and the number of networks. In order to develop strategic networks and to become involved in them, this study suggests that International new ventures need to make valuable connections by taking advantage (if managers & entrepreneurs with good international business experience are available) of personal networks and the previous international business experience of managers & entrepreneurs.

Sialkot Surgical Industry should have strong global linkage and foreign companies should consider the small companies in Sialkot and Sialkot chamber of commerce and SIMAP should take interest to strengthen the surgical industry of Sialkot. The network building is very essential for business as well industry growth.

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